

Bioproducts assessment using quantitative image analysis in a mixed microbial culture fed with used cooking oil

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Abstract

The use of image analysis for the quantification of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) and triacylglycerides (TAGs) produced by a mixed microbial culture fed with used cooking oil was studied. Three different stains were used, the Sudan Black B (SBB), the Nile Blue A (NBA) and the BODIPY™ 493/503. Acquired images were analysed using Matlab R2024b software, and bioproduct (PHA and TAG) accumulation was predicted through partial least squares (PLS) regression. For PHA prediction, the three stains showed good performance, with NBA achieving the best results with a R^2 of 0.93 and a residual prediction deviation (RPD) of 3.57. However, for the prediction of TAG accumulation all stain resulted unreliable, though SBB showed the best results with a R^2 of 0.68 and a RPD of 1.44. These findings demonstrate the feasibility of using different stains for quantification of the accumulated PHA inside microbial cells, but further research is needed to enhance TAG prediction accuracy.

Keywords

BODIPY™ 493/503; nile blue a; polyhydroxyalkanoates; quantitative image analysis; sudan black b; triacylglycerides.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, there has been a growing interest in the circular economy concept and the production of intracellular bio-based materials such as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) and triacylglycerides (TAGs), which have applications in bioplastics and biofuels, respectively. To ensure that the synthesis of these products is economically competitive and environmentally friendly, efficient quantitative sample analysis is essential. Commonly, the accumulation of these bioproducts has been measured by gas chromatography (GC) (Baidurah, 2022), but this method requires hazardous solvents, posing environmental and health risks. Therefore, there is a growing need to develop cleaner and more efficient monitoring methods. Most studies on intracellular bio-based materials have not attempted to automatically extract quantitative data through microscopic image analysis. However, this technique holds significant potential as a non-invasive and rapid method for quantifying different storage bioproducts, thus facilitating the evaluation of these important biotechnological processes (Mesquita et al., 2013). A significant challenge when applying this technique to cultures enriched in PHA- and TAG-storing bacteria, particularly when working with used cooking oil (UCO) as carbon source, is distinguishing between the two bioproducts.

The present study investigated the feasibility of a monitoring technique based on quantitative image analysis (QIA), using three different staining methods for quantifying PHA and TGA accumulation in mixed microbial culture samples taken from a bioreactor fed with used cooking oil as a carbon source. Partial least squares (PLS) regression models were employed, integrating image analysis parameters related to biomass structure with conventional measurements of storage bioproducts. A comparison between PHA and TAG bioproducts prediction ability using all staining procedures was also performed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Staining procedures

Three different stains, Sudan Black B (SBB), Nile Blue A (NBA) and BODIPY™ 493/503, were applied to samples from different laboratory batch assays with a microbial mixed culture fed with used oil as a carbon source. The samples were processed and stained for subsequent image acquisition and analysis. PHA and TAG content to compare to the data obtained by quantification image analysis were measured by the gas chromatography (GC) method (Baidurah, 2022).

The first staining, SBB, was prepared following the protocol of Jenkins et al. (2003). The samples were observed under bright-field microscopy at a 1000x total magnification using immersion oil. The bacteria appeared red while the PHAs and/or TAGs present in the sample were stained blue-black.

The NBA staining followed the method described by Ostle and Holt (1982). The samples were observed using a fluorescence microscope at a 400x total magnification, with constant exposure times and a 540 nm excitation wavelength (Serafim et al., 2002). PHA and TAG appeared red, with intensity corresponding to the compound concentration.

Lastly, BODIPY™ 493/503 staining was prepared following the protocol proposed by Laura Smith (2022). Samples were observed with a fluorescence microscope at a 400x total magnification, with constant exposure times and an excitation wavelength of 488 nm. With this staining, the PHA and TAG appeared green, with the intensity indicating compound concentration.

Image acquisition, processing, and analysis

Images were acquired using an epifluorescence Olympus BX-51 microscope (Olympus, Shinjuku, Japan) and an Olympus DP71 camera (Olympus, Shinjuku, Japan). Images were taken in the upper, middle, and bottom of the slide resulting in 150 images per slide. Images were acquired with cellSens software (Olympus, Shinjuku, Japan), in 1360 × 1024 pixels and 24-bit RGB format.

The image processing and analysis procedure was based on the identification and quantification of bioproduct inclusions using a specifically developed program in Matlab R2024b (The Mathworks, Natick, MA). The developed Matlab program splits the RGB image into the red, green, and blue channels, selecting the optimal channel for each case for further processing. Background correction, segmentation, and post-processing steps were applied to identify the bioproduct regions, and the resulting binary image was used to calculate the morphological parameters of the inclusions, which were then used as predictors for modelling (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Sample of the images obtained with the different stains. A: original image; B: image after segmentation and debris elimination; C: labelled image.

Multivariate statistical analysis

Partial least squares (PLS) regression was applied to predict PHA and TAG concentrations based on the data obtained from the QIA, provided by a routine specifically designed for SBB, NBA, and BODIPY™ 493/503 staining. To prevent overfitting problems in PLS, the maximum number of latent variables (LV) for each model was limited to half the number of training observations (n/2) (Costa et al., 2022). Cross-validation was employed to determine the optimal number of LVs. The model was performed with a total of 18 samples, divided randomly into a training set (67 % of the observations to calibrate the model) and a validation set (33 % of the observations to validate the final model).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data obtained from the PLS analysis of the different stains are shown in Table 1. For each analysis, the regression equation, coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean square error of prediction (RMSEP), and residual prediction deviation (RPD) values were determined. For a great prediction power, it is recommended that the models have a RPD value larger than 3, which represents the ratio between the standard deviation of the observed values and the RMSEP (Melo et al., 2024).

The results obtained indicate a good prediction of PHA inclusions for all stains tested, within the identified model applicability limits. Among the stains studied, the best result for PHA prediction was obtained with NBA, which resulted in a R^2 of 0.93 and the RPD of 3.57, demonstrating high predictive assessment in a study with mixed microbial cultures fed with waste oil. The second-best performance was observed with SBB, with an R^2 of 0.90 and RPD of 2.95. Finally, BODIPY™ 493/503 (R^2 of 0.89 and RPD of 2.94) exhibited the weakest predictive performance among the stains tested. However, despite this limitation, the results were still considered sufficient for the intended analysis, indicating that while it may not offer the same level of reliability as the other stains, it remains a viable option for use.

Nevertheless, other studies have tested some of these stains (e.g., NBA) for predicting PHA synthesis, showing some predictive capacity (Mesquita et al., 2013), although the data range was more limited than in the present study. A broader data range improves predictive accuracy by including a greater diversity of cases.

In contrast, TAG prediction was less reliable with all stains. While SBB yielded the best TAG prediction (R^2 of 0.68 and an RPD of 1.44), the model's predictive assessment was still considered insufficient for reliable quantification of this bioproduct. The relatively low R^2 and RPD values suggest that the model lacks the accuracy required for precise TAG prediction, highlighting the need for further optimization or alternative staining methods to improve prediction capabilities for TAG accumulation. This could be due to the dye's preference for PHA, or the limit range of TAG concentrations obtained in this study (4.44 – 11.29 %). Given the narrow value range, the prediction model is less effective outside of these limits, leading to a decrease in predictive accuracy (Costa et al., 2022).

Table 1. PLS results for the bioproducts studied using the different stains. LV: Latent Variables; R^2 : correlation coefficient (glb: global, trn: training set, val: validation set); RMSEP: Root Mean Squared Error of Prediction; RPD: Residual Prediction Deviation; Min: minimum value percentage; Max: maximum value percentage; PHA: Polyhydroxyalkanoates; TAG: Triacylglycerides.

Staining	Matrix Y	LV	Regression Equation glb	R^2 glb	R^2 trn	R^2 val	RMSEP	RPD	Min	Max
Sudan Black B	PHA	3	Y=1.01x-0.23	0.90	0.95	0.81	3.89	2.95	3.58	45.43
	TAG	3	Y=1.00x+0.25	0.68	0.76	0.86	1.47	1.44	4.44	11.29
	PHA+TAG	3	Y=1.02x-1.37	0.84	0.87	0.90	4.96	2.24	11.84	49.87
Nile Blue A	PHA	3	Y=1.00x-0.27	0.93	0.96	0.88	3.22	3.57	3.58	45.43
	TAG	3	Y=0.76x+1.74	0.42	0.51	0.62	1.97	1.08	4.44	11.29
	PHA+TAG	3	Y=1.01x+0.05	0.88	0.95	0.75	4.21	2.64	11.84	49.87
BODIPY™ 493/503	PHA	2	Y=0.98x+0.13	0.89	0.94	0.79	3.81	2.94	3.58	45.43
	TAG	2	Y=0.47x+3.62	0.43	0.57	0.03	1.64	1.28	4.44	11.29

CONCLUSION

In the present study, the capacity of quantifying the PHA and TAG accumulated intracellularly by a mixed microbial culture fed with used cooking oil was studied using image analysis through different stains. In the case of PHA, the predictive capacity of these analytical methods was demonstrated with a R^2 of 0.93 and a RPD of 3.57 when Nile Blue A (NBA) dye was used. Although NBA showed the best results, all stains presented good predictive performance for this bioproduct. However, none of the tested stains showed enough predictive ability for reliable quantification of TAG, being the highest R^2 value of 0.68 with the Sudan Black B (SBB) stain, with a RPD of 1.44. With these results, the use of the quantitative image analysis for the prediction of PHA content in a mixed microbial culture fed with used oil showed promising results, but a larger number of samples is recommended for reliable results, especially with wider range of TAG accumulation to improve the prediction of this bioproduct.

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